

A Linguistic Analysis of Phonological and Syntactic Development in Early Childhood: A Case Study of Taraya's Language Acquisition

ABSTRACT

The following work aims to explore the nature of imitation and its effect on children's language development, therefore also referencing features of different stages of language acquisition and their relation to imitation. Moreover, the analysis addresses related language acquisition theories and the impact of social aspects on language development.

The analysed text is provided in Appendix A, and is evaluated in terms of related linguistic frameworks, such as phonology, syntax, lexis and pragmatics.

Keywords: *Linguistics, Child Language Acquisition, Psycholinguistics, Language Acquisition Device, Halliday's Functions.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Children fundamentally imitate those around them - caregivers and parents, not only in terms of behavior, but in language patterns as well, leading to the conclusion that environmental and social interactions are important factors and catalysts of language development. Imitation, as well as social contribution, can be found in every language acquisition theory; however, in some of them, input is highlighted as the most substantial factor for a rapid acquisition.

According to David Crystal, children learn things through observation and imitation. Yet, frequently, the words they say or try to express can be semantically ambiguous. To understand this phenomenon, several key aspects should be considered.

2.0 PHONOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

First of all, speaking from a phonological perspective, children may encounter difficulties in pronouncing some words, given that they have yet to fully master oral motor skills. Specific sounds require precise tongue placement, lip shape and jaw positioning, making it tricky for children to pronounce particular units. For example, those containing consonant digraphs, like 'th', 'ch'. Therefore, 'with' might become [wiv], 'chocolate' - /tɒklɪt/, 'there' - /deə/. Owing to this, final consonant deletion is a common occurrence as well: 'please' /pli/.

The following example 'another' /nʌvə/ in 'mum (.) want another /nʌvə/ one' also emphasizes the social factor and suggests the significance of imitation. The /nʌvə/ form is a result of both sound simplification and replication. In a natural flow of speech speakers often skip particular sounds and produce connected speech, which leads to elision as in the example 'want another' - /wɒnə'nʌðə/. Since children may hear words not as isolated units but as collocations, it is not surprising that they mimic elided sounds as well. Moreover, the word 'picture' includes a consonant cluster 'ct' and the sound /t/, which is often complex for children, resulting in /pɪktə/.

3.0 PRAGMATICS

Furthermore, examining the pragmatic field is essential to address the development of language in children. Pragmatics involves knowledge of language as a functional unit in a social environment. As classified by Michael Halliday, children have seven functions of language, among which the main functions are instrumental and regulatory. Instrumental function is used by children to let others know their personal needs and is often represented by demanding and pleading, using words

such as 'need', 'want' or simply repeating the name of the desired object. The regulatory function is used to control actions of others - ordering around.

Pragmatic development is an integral aspect of language acquisition alongside cognitive development and includes developing communicative skills defined by tone, register, politeness, the ability to respond appropriately in different circumstances. Children acquire these gradually, consequently, in some occasions, expressions of respect and simple manners would be omitted. Thus, given the text B1, Taraya's holophrastic stage, also known as the single-word stage, demonstrates how toddlers communicate to get what they want: '*down down*', '*now down down*'. Notice how, in telegraphic and subsequent multi-word stages, when toddlers' vocabulary expands, Taraya's speech begins to contain markers of politeness: '*please me want biscuit*', '*yes (.) thank you*'.

4.0 SYNTAX

Delving further into the analysis, one of the key aspects to address is syntax, specifically the phenomenon of overgeneralization. Throughout the text B2, Taraya repeatedly says '*me want*', '*me draw*', using '*me*' instead of '*I*'. This can be explained through the instrumental and regulatory functions explored above. As the most frequently used functions in the early stages of acquisition, expressions demanding something typically involve the pronoun '*me*': '*give me*', '*look at me*'. Due to this, children associate '*me*' with a universal pronoun for themselves and apply it in every case.

Additionally, some incorrect grammatical structures are considered minor and not crucial for understanding, such as '*nanny like doggie*'. On the other hand, some are more difficult to interpret: '*mum please have chocolate one?*'. This can be attributed to children's limited vocabulary and inability to express themselves fully, which is often caused by omitted grammatical elements.

Equally important are cases when children produce sentences the meaning of which is difficult to interpret. The same sentences can have different meanings and it becomes the parents' objective to try and understand the need of a child. For instance, eighteen-month-old Taraya points at her pacifier '*dum dum*' as illustrated in the text B1. In this case, the mother needs to understand whether her daughter wishes for pacifier or she simply points out its presence, as she does when referring to her father: '*there da*'.

At this stage, children tend to gesticulate as a consequence of, once again, limited lexicon, in order to make others understand them: '*down down* [lifting her arms up to her mother]'. Ultimately, children repeat after adults, but their focus lies primarily on key words - expressions functioning purely grammatically have little to no meaning for them.

5.0 INNATENESS THEORY AND CONCLUSION

Furthermore, it is noteworthy that these factors can be linked to Noam Chomsky's Innateness Theory. It argues that children possess a LAD - language acquisition device, which helps them understand the structure of a language and, therefore, acquire it rapidly. This, in turn, explains why children, even though imitate adults, still can produce non-standard variations of language and make mistakes.

In conclusion, children's attempts to apply regular rules to irregular patterns (e.g 'goed'), overgeneralization, frequent grammatical and lexical mistakes demonstrate their comprehension rather than mere passive mimicry, accentuating the complex process of language development and the indisputable influence of social factor.

6.0 BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Appendix A

"Primary Source"

Topic: Child Language Development

Subtopic: Stages of speech development

All three texts are edited transcripts of Taraya and her mother at their home at different stages of Taraya's language development.

Text B1

Taraya at 18 months old

Taraya: dum dum [pointing at dummy/pacifier]

Taraya: gone [pointing at empty bowl]

Taraya: down down [lifting her arms up to her mother]

Mother: you want to get down?

Taraya: down down (.) now down down

Taraya: bye-bye da [waving to father as she goes upstairs]

Taraya: there /deə/ da [pointing at her father in the mirror]

Text B2

Taraya at 2 and a half years old with her mother in the kitchen

Taraya: me want biscuit

Mother: what do you say?

Taraya: please /pli/ me want biscuit

Mother: ok go and get the tin

[Taraya goes to the cupboard and brings back the biscuit tin]

Taraya: mum mum please have chocolate /tɒklɪt/ one?

Mother: chocolate (.) ok here you go [hands Taraya a chocolate biscuit]

Taraya: ta [eats biscuit]

Taraya: mum (.) want another /nʌvə/ one

Mother: no only one

Taraya: please

Mother: I said no Taraya

Taraya: I need a biscuit

Mother: Taraya that's enough I said no

Taraya and her mother are sitting at the table

Taraya: me draw a picture /pɪktə/

Mother: what do you want to draw?

Taraya: draw doggie for nanny (.) nanny like doggie

Mother: what colour dog do you want to draw?

Taraya: brown and white with /wiv/ big ears

Mother: lovely she'll like that

Text B3

Taraya at 4 years old, role-playing as a weather forecaster. She has a map of England with different weather pictures stuck on it – rain cloud, sun, snow cloud.

Mother: [pretending to be a news reporter] now we go over to Taraya who is going to tell us the weather (.) and go

Taraya: well the cloud is in the north and it's snow over there [Taraya points to the snow cloud on the board]

Taraya: there's about one hundred (.) one hundred one of snow

Mother: what is the weather going to be in the south?

Taraya: gonna (.) it's gonna be nice and sunny (.) look at the sunshine there [points to the picture of the sun] (.) and over there it will rain [points to the rain cloud] (.) hafta go all the way to the top of the weather board now

Mother: would you like to show us the five-day forecast?

Taraya: yes (.) thank you (.) we are going to have a very nice day (.) it's gonna be sunny and hot so you can all go to the beach and swim and have ice cream (.) now back to the news.